

Graphical Abstract

Training-free Sparse Representations of Dense Vectors for Scalable Information Retrieval

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Highlights

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- Training-free sparse transform of dense vectors for scalable information retrieval
- We allow custom-sized vocabularies in the sparse space for improved flexibility
- Better effectiveness-performance trade-offs than other training-free representations

Training-free Sparse Representations of Dense Vectors for Scalable Information Retrieval

Fabio Carrara^{a,*}, Lucia Vadicamo^a, Giuseppe Amato^a, Claudio Gennaro^a

^a*Institute of Information Science and Technologies, CNR, Via G. Moruzzi 1, Pisa, 56124, , Italy*

Abstract

In this paper, we propose and analyze Vec2Doc, a novel training-free method to transform dense vectors into sparse integer vectors, facilitating the use of inverted indexes for information retrieval (IR). The exponential growth of deep learning and artificial intelligence has revolutionized scientific problem-solving in areas such as computer vision, natural language processing, and automatic content generation. These advances have also significantly impacted IR, with a better understanding of natural language and multimodal content analysis leading to more accurate information retrieval. Despite these developments, modern IR relies primarily on the similarity evaluation of dense vectors from the latent spaces of deep neural networks. This dependence introduces substantial challenges in performing similarity searches on large collections containing billions of vectors. Traditional IR methods, which employ inverted indexes and vector space models, are adept at handling sparse vectors but do not work well with dense ones. Vec2Doc attempts to fill this gap by converting dense vectors into a format compatible with conventional inverted index techniques. Our preliminary experimental evaluations show that Vec2Doc is a promising solution to overcome the scalability problems inherent in vector-based IR, offering an alternative method for efficient and accurate large-scale information retrieval.

Keywords: Inverted Index, Approximate Search, High-Dimensional Indexing, Very Large Databases, Surrogate Text Representation

1. Introduction

Dense learned representations are foundational for retrieval tasks over a large span of data modalities. In large-scale settings, the most effective methodologies to retrieve text documents, images, videos, etc., are based on computing vector similarity, i.e., cosine similarity, between queries and data points representations extracted by neural models such as large multimodal/language [1, 2] or common-space models [3, 4, 5].

However, the nature of neural representations poses challenges in indexing and querying large collections. Tested and mature technology for web-scale retrieval is based on inverted indices and assumes sparse, high-dimensional, and positive vector representations. Instead, neural representations are often dense, signed, and lower-dimensional, making

the direct application of inverted indices very inefficient. Dense retrieval approaches based on approximate nearest neighbor provide exceptional performance, but those solutions usually scale worse than disk-based inverted-file implementations, in terms of cost, as they often require more expensive resources like a high RAM usage or GPU acceleration. For large-scale collections, disk-based indices based on sparse dot products still offer an inexpensive solution. Methods such as SparTerm [6] and SPLADE [7, 8] have been proposed for learning sparse representations with wanted properties, but they require a costly training procedure for each collection we want to index.

Other works explored instead *training-free* methods to obtain sparse representations from the dense ones as faster and more general alternatives to learning-based approaches. These include *Surrogate Text Representations* (STR) — sparse representations that can be interpreted as term-frequency integer vectors and expressed as a string

*Corresponding author

of tokens in a custom vocabulary. This enables the ingest of specially crafted textual documents representing a generic dense vector into existing fully-featured text search engines like Elasticsearch and Apache Solr and implements any modal retrieval without a dedicated software stack. [This approach ensures scalability and interoperability with widely adopted search infrastructures.](#)

In this work, we propose and evaluate [Vec2Doc](#), an improved training-free dense-to-sparse transformation of vectors for maximum inner product search problems. Specifically, we [address a key limitation of existing STR methods based on scalar quantization \[9\], which have a fixed-size output dimensionality. To overcome this, we introduced a conceptually simple yet highly effective technique that enables an arbitrary choice of the number of dimensions in the sparse transformed space. This flexibility in output dimensionality is crucial as it enables a better balance between efficiency and retrieval effectiveness. This is demonstrated by the performance improvements of our approach, which we evaluate across multiple benchmarks for approximate nearest neighbor search on dense features, showing that increasing the dimensionality of the sparse representation consistently enhances the effectiveness-efficiency trade-off.](#)

A concrete demonstration of the practical impact of our approach is its successful integration into the 2024 release of VISIONE [10, 11, 12], an interactive video retrieval system (demo available on 2,300 hours of diverse video content at <https://visione.isti.cnr.it/>). VISIONE relies on Lucene for indexing and searching multi-modal content, leveraging Vec2Doc to create a unified retrieval framework that combines semantic search over neural features with text-based metadata in a scalable manner. The effectiveness of this integration has been validated through participation in international benchmarking campaigns, including the Video Browser Showdown (VBS) [13, 14], where VISIONE ranked first in the 2024 edition [15], achieving the best interactive video search system score in four out of seven retrieval tasks. This real-world deployment showcases the practical applicability of Vec2Doc, confirming its effectiveness in large-scale retrieval engines and its potential for real-world adoption.

A preliminary version of this work appeared in [16]. The present contribution provides a more detailed description of the proposed approach and an extensive experimental evaluation, including new results on [a large scale dataset](#), cross-modal search

[scenarios](#), and a discussion of current limitations. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides background and discusses related work. Section 3 presents the proposed Vec2Doc approach, Section 4 details the experimental setup and discusses results and limitations, and Section 5 concludes the paper and outlines directions for future research. Table 1 summarizes the notation used throughout the paper.

2. Background and Related Work

Metric search, essential for retrieving data objects close to a given query object under a proximity function, finds wide application across various fields of computer science, including pattern recognition, computational biology, and multimedia information retrieval. This paradigm operates on the premise that data objects belong to a domain equipped with a *metric* function that quantifies the closeness between objects [18]. Within this framework, the concept of *similarity search* arises naturally, where the goal shifts to identifying data objects similar to a given query object based on a similarity measure derived from the domain’s metric function.

To overcome challenges posed by large or high-dimensional datasets, where exact search becomes impractical due to the need to analyze substantial data portions, *approximate metric search* methods have emerged. These methods address issues such as the curse of dimensionality [19] by offering efficient search techniques that balance computational efficiency with acceptable accuracy. Most of these approaches involve transforming original data objects into alternative representations to enable more efficient searching. Examples of such techniques include transforming metric objects into binary sketches [20, 21], permutations [22, 23], and other pivot-based representations [24, 25].

In 2010, Gennaro et al. [26] introduced a technique that utilized the distances between data objects and a set of reference objects (pivots) to map the data into a textual representation. Their objective was to convert a global descriptor into a sequence of terms resembling a text document, which could be processed by a text search engine such as Lucene. To achieve this, the mapping should be designed to approximate the original distance function, ensuring that the distance between textual documents and queries reflects the original similarity between data objects and data queries.

Table 1: Notation used throughout this paper

Symbol	Definition
$f : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^m$	Space transformation
$\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^d$	d -dimensional real vector
$\bar{\mathbf{y}} = f(\mathbf{y}) \in \mathbb{N}^m$	Integer-valued vector (term frequency vector) obtained from \mathbf{y} using the space transformation f
$\mathcal{C} = \{\tau_1, \dots, \tau_m\}$	Synthetic codebook of m terms
$T_{f,\mathcal{C}}(\mathbf{y})$	Text document for the vector \mathbf{y} associated to the transformation f and the codebook \mathcal{C}
$A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times d}$	Semi-orthogonal matrix (i.e., $A^T A = I$) with $m > d$
$R \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$	Random orthogonal matrix
$\text{CReLU} : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{2n}$	Concatenated Rectified Linear Unit transformation [17], i.e., $\text{CReLU}(\mathbf{y}) = \max([\mathbf{y}, -\mathbf{y}], \mathbf{0})$
$g : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$	Sparsification function
$\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$	Floor function
$ \cdot $	Set cardinality
$\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$	Dot product

Figure 1: Illustration depicting the fundamental steps of an STR technique transforming a dense vector into a text representation suitable for indexing, leveraging a full-text search engine like Lucene

141 The main advantage of encoding data objects as 156
 142 text was the ability to leverage off-the-shelf text 157
 143 retrieval engines for performing similarity searches. 158
 144 This approach was initially referred to as the *Sur-* 159
 145 *rogate Text Representation* (STR) approach. How- 160
 146 ever, over the years, various techniques have been 161
 147 proposed to transform descriptors into textual doc- 162
 148 uments, and the term STR has come to encom- 163
 149 pass the broader family of approaches of this nature 164
 150 [9, 27, 28]. Some of these techniques have been 165
 151 designed to work on general metric spaces, while oth- 166
 152 ers are specialized for vector spaces. 167

153 In this work, our focus is on STR techniques spe- 168
 154 cialized to index and search *dense real vectors*, such 169
 155 as data descriptors extracted with deep neural net- 170

works. These techniques can be mathematically 156
 formalized as space transformations of the form $f : 157$
 $\mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^m$, where each original vector \mathbf{y} is mapped 158
 into an integer-valued vector $\bar{\mathbf{y}} = f(\mathbf{y})$. The key 159
 idea is to interpret $\bar{\mathbf{y}}$ as a term frequency vector 160
 based on a synthetic codebook $\mathcal{C} = \{\tau_1, \dots, \tau_m\}$ of 161
 m terms. Consequently, the associated text docu- 162
 ment for vector \mathbf{y} is obtained by concatenating the 163
 codebook terms with space separators, where each 164
 term τ_i is repeated a number of times equal to \bar{y}_i . 165
 We indicate with $T_{f,\mathcal{C}}(\cdot)$ the overall transformation 166
 from the original vectors to the text documents, 167
 which depends on both the function f and the used 168
 codebook \mathcal{C} . For example, if $\bar{\mathbf{y}} = [3, 1, 0, 2]$ and 169
 $\mathcal{C} = \{“A”, “B”, “C”, “D”\}$, the resulting text doc- 170

171 ument associated with \mathbf{y} would be $T_{f,c}(\mathbf{y}) = \text{“A A A}$
 172 B D D” . The rationale behind this approach is that
 173 the abstract transformation f corresponds to the
 174 function that precisely generates the vectors used
 175 internally by the search engine based on the *vector*
 176 *space model* [29], particularly in the case of a sim-
 177 ple TF-weighting scheme. Figure 1 broadly sum-
 178 marizes the core idea behind the STR techniques.

179 To ensure compatibility with text retrieval en-
 180 gines and the efficiency of the inverted index, f
 181 must generate a sparse vector with non-negative
 182 components. Various STR approaches exist, differ-
 183 ing in their specific methods for handling negative
 184 values, achieving sparsification, and performing the
 185 final real-to-integer discretization. For example, in
 186 [9, 28], the use of the Concatenated Rectified Lin-
 187 ear Unit (CReLU) activation function is employed
 188 to prevent the presence of negative values in the
 189 transformed vectors. In [28], a Voronoi partition-
 190 ing scheme is employed, where different codebooks
 191 are utilized for each partition. This approach aims
 192 to increase the sparsity of the transformed data,
 193 leading to more efficient indexing and retrieval pro-
 194 cesses.

195 Several works explored learned sparse represen-
 196 tations [30, 6, 7, 8], where learning-to-rank proce-
 197 dures with sparsity constraints are used to learn f ,
 198 often obtaining very efficient and effective inverted
 199 indices. However, the price is often paid in longer
 200 index training procedures that require optimiza-
 201 tion on labeled datasets or mined triplets of sam-
 202 ples for each indexed collection. Moreover, these
 203 methods are tailored to the textual modality, and
 204 the obtained representations are often constrained
 205 in their dimensionality by the explicit vocabulary
 206 on which they are trained, e.g., the token space of
 207 large language models, which, despite being big, is
 208 not changeable. Our proposal is instead an explora-
 209 tion of the effectiveness-efficiency trade-off we can
 210 obtain using *training-free* methods to obtain repre-
 211 sentation with a custom number of dimensions and
 212 sparsity level.

213 3. Vec2Doc

214 The Vec2Doc is a STR transformation that maps
 215 a dense real vector $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ into a term frequency
 216 vector $\bar{\mathbf{y}} \in \mathbb{N}^m$. This transformation involves four
 217 main steps defined in the following paragraphs and
 218 summarized in Figure 2.

1. Semi-orthogonal transformation.

$$219 \mathbf{y}_1 = A\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^m, \quad (1)$$

where $A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times d}$ is a semi-orthogonal matrix (i.e.,
 $A^T A = I$) with $m > d$. The purpose of this trans-
 formation is to increase the vector dimensionality
 while preserving the dot product:

$$220 \langle A\mathbf{v}, A\mathbf{w} \rangle = \mathbf{v}^T A^T A \mathbf{w} = \mathbf{v}^T \mathbf{w} = \langle \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w} \rangle .$$

221 This step has two significant implications. First,
 222 it allows the dimensionality of the original vector
 223 to be disentangled from that of the final frequency
 224 vector, enabling the use of a vocabulary of arbitrary
 225 dimensions. Second, since the semi-orthogonal ma-
 226 trix is randomly chosen, it behaves similarly to a
 227 random rotation, effectively distributing informa-
 228 tion across the different dimensional components.
 229 To sample a random semi-orthogonal matrix, we
 230 follow [31] and apply the following recurrent for-
 231 mula to a random normally-distributed real-valued
 232 matrix

$$233 A \leftarrow A - \frac{1}{2} A (A^T A - I) \quad (2)$$

234 that efficiently converge into a semi-orthogonal ma-
 235 trix in a few iterations.

236 2. *Positivization.* Since the final vector must be
 237 positive (as it represents frequencies), a crucial step
 238 is to positivize \mathbf{y}_1 without significantly degrading
 239 the preservation of similarities between data pairs.
 240 Various functions have been tested, including Rec-
 241 tified Linear Unit (ReLU), Concatenated Rectified
 242 Linear Unit (CReLU), element-wise logistic func-
 243 tion σ , and softmax. The approach that gave the
 244 best results and was chosen is based on the use of
 245 CReLU [17]:

$$246 \mathbf{y}_2 = \text{CReLU}(\mathbf{y}_1) \in \mathbb{R}^{2m}. \quad (3)$$

247 The CReLU transformation involves concatenating
 248 both the original vector and its negation and then
 249 setting all negative values to zero, i.e., $\text{CReLU}(\mathbf{v}) =$
 250 $\max([\mathbf{v}, -\mathbf{v}], \mathbf{0})$ with the max operation applied
 251 element-wise.

252 3. *Sparsification.* $\mathbf{y}_3 = g(\mathbf{y}_2) \in \mathbb{R}^{2m}$, where g is
 253 a sparification function. This step is crucial be-
 254 cause the data will be indexed using inverted lists,
 255 and the frequency vectors must be sparse to ensure
 256 each data item is saved in only a limited number
 257 of posting lists. This process attempts to replicate

Figure 2: Illustration of the four basic steps of the Vec2Doc method.

254 the natural occurrence in texts, where a single doc- 280
 255 ument contains only a few vocabulary words, res-
 256 sulting in sparse frequency vectors. We explored
 257 three different approaches for sparsification:

- 258 • *Top-K selection*: For a fixed k , retain only the
 259 k elements with the largest magnitudes (those
 260 contributing most significantly to the dot prod-
 261 uct) and set the rest to zero.
- 262 • *Fixed thresholding*: Use a fixed threshold γ and
 263 set all values smaller than this threshold to
 264 zero.
- 265 • *α -norm-mass selection [32]*: Retain the least
 266 number of largest-magnitude components such
 267 that the norm of the resulting vector is a given
 268 fraction $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ of the original norm (e.g.,
 269 maintaining 75% of the norm).

270 Experimentally, we noticed no significant differ- 297
 271 ences between these sparsification methods on the 298
 272 tested datasets, achieving all the same efficiency- 299
 273 effectiveness trade-off curves. We will consider the
 274 Top-K selection method in the following, as it gives
 275 explicit control over the index size with the k pa-
 276 rameter regardless of data distribution.

277 4. *Integer Quantization*. $\mathbf{y}_4 = \lfloor s \mathbf{y}_3 \rfloor \in \mathbb{N}^{2m}$ where
 278 $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ denotes the floor function and $s > 1$ is a *quan-*
 279 *tization factor* to transform float components into

integers¹.

Vec2Doc can be seen as a generalization of the Scalar Quantization (SQ) STR approach [9]. Specifically, in SQ, $\mathbf{y}_1 = R(\mathbf{y} - \boldsymbol{\mu}) \in \mathbb{R}^d$ where $R \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ is a random orthogonal matrix and $\boldsymbol{\mu} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is set to center the data to zero mean. This step is used to uniform the distribution of vector components. In particular, the random rotation helps distribute the information along all the components of the vector in order to limit the presence of unbalanced posting lists in the final inverted file (important for the efficiency of inverted indices). In [9], the centering operation is applied only to the data object but not to the queries to preserve dot-product similarities. The primary drawback of the SQ approach is its limitation in terms of the dimensionality of the resulting term frequency vectors, which is fixed at $2d$, where d represents the dimensionality of the original vector. Consequently, the vocabulary size necessary for indexing the data

¹Integer quantization is introduced for the simple purpose of to express feature vectors as integers, allowing us to interpret them as term frequencies to be integrated into text search engines. This step is necessary only when floating-point values cannot be stored directly, and we, therefore, use the surrogate document approach. In any case, this approximation has a negligible impact on search accuracy.

Dataset	Dim.	$ Q $	$ X $	OOD
Glove	100	10,000	1,183,514	✗
NYTimes	256	10,000	290,000	✗
LAION2B-CLIP768v2	768	10,000	102,144,212	✗
COCO i2i	512	5,000	118,287	✗
COCO t2i	512	5,000	118,287	✓

Table 2: **Approximate nearest neighbors datasets.** $|Q|$ = number of queries, $|X|$ = number of samples in the search set, OOD = whether the queries are out-of-distribution with respect to search-set samples.

with inverted files remains constant, posing an inconvenience when dealing with large datasets. To clarify further, if the number of posting lists is fixed, the length of each posting list may become excessive for large datasets, ultimately impacting search efficiency negatively. To address these limitations, [28] introduced the VP-SQ approach, where the data is clustered in Voronoi cells, and a different vocabulary can be used for each cell. Here, we propose a simple yet effective idea to expand the vocabulary size using semi-orthogonal transformation instead of centroids. Nevertheless, our new Vec2Doc approach can be used alone or in combination with Voronoi partitioning strategies to further improve performance. Please note that the semi-orthogonal transformation is applied to both data and query vectors (without centering the former) before the real-to-integer discretization process.

4. Experiments

In this section, we present the results of our experimental analysis, which evaluates the performance of the proposed STR method under various scenarios. We first introduce the experimental setup, followed by an in-depth discussion and analysis of the results obtained in both an implementation-independent scenario and a Lucene-based implementation. To facilitate reproducibility and practical adoption, the complete implementation of our method is publicly available at <https://github.com/fabiocarrara/str-encoders>.

4.1. Experimental Setup

Datasets. We evaluated and compared our proposal on five benchmarks for approximate nearest neighbor search whose characteristics are reported in Table 2. Glove [33] and NYTimes [34] are existing collections of dense embeddings of textual documents. LAION2B is a publicly available large-scale

dataset derived from LAION-5B [35], widely used for training and evaluating large vision-language models. We use the 100M image subset of the English portion of LAION2B (LAION2B-CLIP768v2), represented by 768-dimensional CLIP embeddings [36], employed in the SISAP 2024 Indexing Challenge ². To evaluate performance in both intra-modal and cross-modal settings, where queries may be out-of-distribution with respect to the search set samples, we additionally constructed two collections by extracting CLIP [36] features (specifically, the CLS output token of OpenAI’s ViT-B/16 architecture) from the COCO dataset [37]. These collections simulate common query-by-example and text-based image retrieval scenarios. Specifically, we extract CLIP visual features from training-set images to be used as the search set. Then, we extract visual and textual features from the validation-set images and relative captions (only the first one out of five available for each image) to be used as queries. When using visual embeddings as queries, we refer to the image-to-image (i2i) scenario, while in the text-to-image (t2i) scenario, we adopt captions embeddings as queries. The t2i scenario has the peculiarity of having different distributions of query and search-set samples. All collections adopt the cosine similarity to compare feature vectors. We L_2 -normalize all vectors and compute cosine similarity scores as inner products.

Evaluation Metrics. We report three main metrics to quantify the effectiveness and efficiency of each tested configuration, which are:

Recall@K the fraction of ground-truth nearest neighbors present in the top $K \in \{1, 10, 100\}$ retrieved results.

Search Cost the number of entries accessed in the inverted index needed to compute scores for all queries (also referred to in the literature as AFDA [27] or FLOPS [38]).

Index Size the total number of entries in the inverted index.

Additionally, for machine- and implementation-dependent results (Section 4.2.2), we report the index build time, the average query time, and the index size in bytes.

Figure 3: **Effectiveness (Recall@K) versus Search Cost (number of posts accessed to compute scores) on Glove 100 (a), NYTimes 256 (b), and LAION2B-CLIP768v2 (c) benchmarks.** We compare our proposed method with the SQ baseline [9]. Each line is obtained by choosing the desired vocabulary size m and varying k — the number of components kept per vector after sparsification. the black dashed line represents the search cost for a sequential search on the respective dataset, providing a reference point to highlight configurations where the cost exceeds that of a brute-force approach. Additionally, a red vertical band marks the region where the search cost ranges between 1% and 10% of a sequential search, representing a reasonable computational budget for practical retrieval scenarios.

Figure 4: **Effectiveness (Recall@K) versus Index Size (# of entries in the index) on Glove 100 (a), NYTimes 256 (b), and LAION2B-CLIP768v2 (c) benchmarks.** We compare our proposed method with the SQ baseline [9]. Each line is obtained by choosing the desired vocabulary size m and varying k — the number of components kept per vector after sparsification. The black dashed line represents the size of the original dataset (no index).

4.2. Results and Discussion

In the following, we present the experimental evaluation of our approach. We first analyze the results in a machine- and implementation-independent setting, where recall is assessed as a function of search cost, measured by counting the number of accessed entries in the inverted index. This approach ensures that performance comparisons are not affected by the specific implementation details of the inverted index.

We then complement this analysis with results obtained using a Lucene³-based implementation, highlighting the correlation between the number of accessed posting list entries and the actual retrieval efficiency in a real-world indexing system. This additional evaluation provides insights into the practical impact of our method in an operational environment.

Finally, we discuss some limitations of our approach and outline potential future directions to improve robustness in scenarios where query and database distributions differ significantly.

4.2.1. Implementation-Independent Performance Evaluation

In Figures 3 and 4, we compared our improved STR scheme against the SQ-based STR approach [9] in a machine- and implementation-independent setting over three benchmarks: Glove 100, NYTimes 256 and the large-scale LAION2B-CLIP768v2. Each line is obtained by choosing the desired vocabulary size (i.e., the number of rows m of the semi-orthogonal transformation A in Equation 1) and varying the number k of elements that are not zeroed in the vector sparsification step. Specifically, in these plots, each point represents a different sparsification threshold k , while the colors of the lines indicate different vocabulary sizes m . Figure 3 presents the comparison in terms of Recall@K vs. Search Cost. Since both the vocabulary size m and the parameter k can significantly impact the search cost, for better clarity, the figure also includes a black dashed line indicating the search cost for a sequential search on the same dataset. This serves as a reference, as configurations with a higher cost than a sequential scan are not of practical interest. Additionally, each figure includes a red vertical band, which marks the region where the search cost

ranges between 1% and 10% of a sequential search. This range represents a reasonable computational budget for practical retrieval applications. By focusing on this cost range, it becomes evident that our proposed method achieves a significantly better trade-off between effectiveness and search cost, offering up to $\sim 100\times$ search cost reduction with marginal or no recall degradation, particularly in medium-to-low search cost configurations.

However, we acknowledge certain limitations of our approach, including scalability concerns related to index size and the challenges posed by excessive dimensionality expansion.

First, the improvement in efficiency comes at the cost of an increased index size that can reach $\sim 100\times$ the original size in high-recall configurations (Figure 4). This was expected due to the increase in dimensionality brought by Vec2Doc, though disk-based inverted-index implementations are cheaper to scale than main memory-based indices implementations like FAISS [39]. Still, this limits the application of Vec2Doc in extreme cases, i.e., in low-sparsity, high-recall settings.

Second, we note diminishing returns using higher values of the dimension multiplier m . We note a linear increase of the recall-cost curve in the positive recall (y-axis) direction while scaling m exponentially (doubling it). However, the cost of applying the Vec2Doc transformation depends linearly on m , thus prohibiting higher m values.

Given these factors, our Vec2Doc results particularly well-suited for the first stage of multi-stage retrieval pipelines, where initial candidate retrieval is performed efficiently before applying more computationally intensive reranking methods on the original features. Therefore, our approach is designed as a first-stage solution, providing a fast and scalable retrieval mechanism that can be seamlessly integrated with any subsequent refinement stage to further improve retrieval performance.

4.2.2. Evaluation with a Lucene-Based Implementation

We test our method on a disk-based inverted-file implementation based on Apache Lucene. We encode and generate surrogate documents for each sample in the search set and query set. We configure the Lucene searching procedures to use a TF-only similarity to implement inner product scoring. Scores (and thus Recall@K) computed with the Lucene implementation coincide with the one

²<https://sisap-challenges.github.io/2024/>

³<https://lucene.apache.org/>

(a) Recall@10 vs Query Time

(b) Recall@10 vs Index Size

(c) Query Time vs Estimated Search Cost
 (Query Time (s) $\approx 10^{-12} \cdot$ Search Cost $+ 2 \cdot 10^{-2}$)

Figure 5: Results obtained by a Lucene-based Implementation (single-thread on 2GHz CPU and SSD drive) on Glove-100.

480 computed in Section 4.2.1 up to small rounding errors.
 481 Experiments were conducted with a single
 482 thread on a Ubuntu machine with a CPU Intel®
 483 Xeon® Platinum 8480C Processor 2.0 GHz and
 484 an SSD disk. We measure the recall@10, the average
 485 query time, and the index build time and size. Figure 5
 486 reports the results for the Glove-100 dataset, while Table 3
 487 reports the results on LAION2B-CLIP768v2 for some
 488 configurations in the best recall-cost curve in Figure 3c
 489 ($m = 50$). We note that the effectiveness vs query time
 490 (Figure 5a) and index size (Figure 5b) follow the exact
 491 same trends shown in Figure 3a and 4a. Moreover, as
 492 expected, we observe a linear relationship between the
 493 implementation-independent search cost metric and the
 494 actual query time, independently from the choice of
 495 parameters of Vec2Doc (Figure 5c).
 496

4.2.3. Impact of Distribution Shifts in Retrieval Performance

497 In this section, we examine the impact of distribution
 498 shifts between query and database sample distributions,
 499 particularly in cross-modal retrieval tasks. We observe
 500 degraded effectiveness when dealing with cross-modal
 501 datasets having different query and database sample
 502 distributions. Comparing the recall-cost curves for the
 503 COCO dataset in image-to-image (Figure 6a) and text-to-
 504 image (Figure 6b) retrieval settings, we can see Vec2Doc
 505 struggling in the latter. In the inter-modal text-to-
 506 image setting, queries and database vectors are extracted
 507 respectively from text and images using two different
 508 encoders that, despite sharing a common output space,
 509 do not produce the same distributions for the two modalities.
 510 In turn, this produces a cosine similarity score distribution
 511 between queries and nearest neighbors that does not cover
 512 values greater than 0.4, while the highest scores in
 513 intra-modal settings are near 1.0. Analyzing Vec2Doc
 514 under this distribution shift, we deem the positization
 515 step implemented by the CReLU transformation (Equation
 516 3) to be the main culprit for the performance degradation.
 517 Indeed, the CReLU transformation tends to preserve cosine
 518 similarities when they tend to 1 due to the alignment of
 519 same-sign components in the original and transformed
 520 vectors. At the same time, it increasingly distorts scores
 521 as the number of mixed-sign components in the inner
 522 product increases, i.e., as the original cosine score
 523 decreases. Figure 7 shows the distribution of scores
 524 before and after the CReLU transformation in our datasets.
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Figure 6: **Results on COCO CLIP image-to-image (top) and text-to-image (bottom) benchmarks.** We show Effectiveness (Recall@K) vs. Search Cost (# of posts visited to compute scores) and Index Size (# of entries in the index) of our proposal and of the SQ baseline [9]. Each line is obtained by choosing the desired vocabulary size m and varying k — the number of components kept per vector after sparsification.

m	k	Search Cost	Num. Entries	Query time (s)	Build time	Index size	R@10
50	25	517.9B (0.1%)	2.6B (3.3%)	0.448 ± 0.211	2h 14m 49s	6.6GB	20.2%
50	50	1.4T (0.2%)	5.1B (6.5%)	1.309 ± 0.564	2h 24m 12s	12.3GB	31.9%
50	100	3.7T (0.5%)	10.2B (13.0%)	4.146 ± 1.473	3h 26m 08s	23.4GB	45.0%
50	250	13.9T (1.8%)	25.6B (32.6%)	14.052 ± 3.661	6h 43m 59s	55.1GB	60.5%

Table 3: Results obtained by a Lucene-based Implementation (single-thread on 2GHz CPU and SSD drive) on LAION2B-CLIP768v2. Query Time (s) $\approx 10^{-12} \cdot$ Search Cost + $3 \cdot 10^{-2}$

531 For intra-modal datasets (7a, 7c, 7b), the original 532
533 and transformed scores between queries and near- 534
535 est neighbors tend to lie on the $y = x$ line near 536
537 the top right corner, indicating only small distortions 538
539 of scores introduced by Vec2Doc. Instead, in cross-modal 540
541 retrieval (Figure 7d), the CReLU transformation 542
543 increases the overlap between nearest neighbor and random 544
545 samples score distributions, leading to degraded recall 546
547 performance.

548 *Exploring Alternative Positivization Functions.* To 549
550 address the challenges observed in the cross-modal 551
552 retrieval, we investigated several alternative functions 553
554 for vector positivization beyond CReLU, including 555
556 ReLU, exponential, softmax, and logistic transformations, 557
558 both with and without L1 normalization. ReLU slightly 559
560 underperformed compared to CReLU, as previously noted in [9]. 561
562 Non-normalized transformations, such as the exponential 563
564 function ($f(x) = e^{x/T}$) and the logistic function 565
566 ($f(x) = 1/(1 + e^{-x/T})$), where T is a temperature 567
568 parameter controlling the transformation, resulted in a 569
570 significant performance drop. These methods failed to 571
572 preserve the inner product structure, leading to degraded 573
574 retrieval effectiveness.

575 Among the tested alternatives, the L1-normalized 576
577 logistic transformation initially appeared promising, 578
579 showing the potential to outperform CReLU in specific 580
581 temperature settings. However, further analysis revealed a 582
583 critical drawback: while this function enhanced the 584
585 positivization step, it led to a severe drop in recall 586
587 when combined with the sparsification process. The softmax 588
589 function (i.e., L1-normalized exponential), on the other 590
591 hand, yielded optimal results only in specific datasets and 592
593 configurations. However, it exhibited very low recall when 594
595 applied to the positivization of certain types of features, 596
597 particularly CLIP embeddings, where its transformation 598
599 appeared to overly compress similarity distributions, 600
601 severely reducing retrieval effectiveness.

602 Given these observations, we concluded that, despite 603
604 its limitations in cross-modal scenarios, CReLU remains 605
606 the most suitable choice among the tested methods, 607
608 ensuring applicability across different data types. 609
610 Nonetheless, developing a positivization and sparsification 611
612 strategy that better preserves accuracy even under 613
614 distributional shifts remains an open challenge for future 615
616 research.

617 *Results Summary and Parameter Tuning.* Table 4 618
619 provides a summary of the results for Search Cost, 620
621 Index Size, and Recall for selected values of the 622
623 parameters k and m . For each of the tested values 624
625 of m , we report the configurations that achieve the 626
627 closest search cost level to 5% of the reference cost. 628
629 Unlike the plots shown in the previous figures, which 630
631 offer a general overview of performance trends across 632
633 various datasets and parameter settings, the table allows 634
635 for a more precise understanding of the parameter values 636
637 used to achieve a desired search cost and the corresponding 638
639 recall in the different tested scenarios.

640 5. Conclusion

641 Vec2Doc is a novel method for converting dense 642
643 vectors obtained from neural networks into sparse 644
645 representations, specifically designed to address the 646
647 challenges of large-scale feature information retrieval. 648
649 In the proposed approach, we focus specifically on STR 650
651 encoding by decoupling the size of the vocabulary to the 652
653 size of the dense vectors, thus improving the efficiency 654
655 of the search.

656 Through our experiments, we have demonstrated the 657
658 validity of our approach, especially in the context of 659
660 image-to-image queries. However, there are limitations 661
662 and open challenges that we acknowledge and plan to 663
664 explore in future work. A key aspect is the handling of 665
666 out-of-distribution queries, particularly in cross-modal 667
668 retrieval settings, where differences in feature 669
670 distributions affect retrieval performance. To address 671
672 this, we plan to investigate the alternative combinations 673
674 of feature transformation and sparsification techniques 675
676 that are better suited for such scenarios. Beyond this, 677
678 we also recognize the importance of scalability and 679
680 intend to explore Vec2Doc integration into multi-stage 681
682 retrieval pipelines to enhance its applicability and 683
684 performance on very large datasets.

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Figure 7: Joint and marginal distributions of scores computed with and without the CReLU positization function. We report distributions of scores computed between queries and the first 100 nearest neighbors (in blue) and between queries and random samples from the search set (in green).

Table 4: Summary of the results for Search Cost, Index Size, and Recall for selected values of the parameters k and m . Percentages in parentheses refer to the reference cost and size of the full dense index. The table shows configurations that achieve search cost levels as close as possible to 5%.

m	k	Search Cost (# posts visited)	Index Size (# entries)	Recall@10
Glove 100				
1	25	51.5B (4.4%)	29.6M (25.0%)	16.9%
2	40	68.7B (5.8%)	47.3M (40.0%)	23.1%
5	50	49.9B (4.2%)	59.2M (50.0%)	24.2%
10	70	55.5B (4.7%)	82.8M (70.0%)	29.4%
20	100	61.5B (5.2%)	118.4M (100.0%)	36.0%
50	100	31.7B (2.7%)	118.4M (100.0%)	35.1%
100	200	62.7B (5.3%)	236.7M (200.0%)	48.2%
NYTimes 256				
1	77	34.0B (4.6%)	22.0M (29.7%)	50.3%
2	102	31.0B (4.2%)	29.6M (39.8%)	51.8%
5	179	38.9B (5.2%)	51.9M (69.9%)	58.6%
10	256	40.4B (5.4%)	74.2M (100.0%)	62.4%
20	256	20.9B (2.8%)	74.2M (100.0%)	60.3%
50	512	34.0B (4.6%)	148.5M (200.0%)	69.2%
100	512	17.8B (2.4%)	148.5M (200.0%)	67.7%
COCO CLIP 512 image-to-image				
1	51	7.7B (2.5%)	6.0M (10.0%)	33.8%
2	128	21.0B (6.9%)	15.1M (25.0%)	52.6%
5	128	14.3B (4.7%)	15.1M (25.0%)	52.7%
10	154	14.6B (4.8%)	18.1M (29.9%)	55.7%
20	205	16.4B (5.4%)	24.1M (39.8%)	60.8%
50	256	15.5B (5.1%)	30.3M (50.0%)	65.1%
100	250	11.2B (3.7%)	29.6M (48.8%)	65.4%
COCO CLIP 512 text-to-image				
1	128	14.1B (4.7%)	15.1M (25.0%)	9.4%
2	154	12.2B (4.0%)	18.1M (29.9%)	10.1%
5	256	13.9B (4.6%)	30.3M (50.0%)	14.9%
10	358	14.2B (4.7%)	42.3M (69.9%)	18.3%
20	512	15.6B (5.2%)	60.6M (100.0%)	22.3%
50	512	7.7B (2.5%)	60.6M (100.0%)	19.4%
100	1024	15.5B (5.1%)	121.1M (200.0%)	31.7%
LAION2B-CLIP768v2				
1	100	22.2T (2.8%)	10.2B (13.0%)	43.3%
2	250	60.5T (7.7%)	25.5B (32.6%)	60.5%
5	250	40.2T (5.1%)	25.5B (32.6%)	59.7%
10	250	29.3T (3.7%)	25.5B (32.6%)	60.1%
20	500	57.3T (7.3%)	51.1B (65.1%)	70.3%
50	500	37.6T (4.8%)	51.1B (65.1%)	70.7%

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References

[1] J. Devlin, M.-W. Chang, K. Lee, K. Toutanova, BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding, in: Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, Volume 1 (Long and Short Papers), 2019, pp. 4171–4186.

[2] Y. Chang, X. Wang, J. Wang, Y. Wu, L. Yang, K. Zhu, H. Chen, X. Yi, C. Wang, Y. Wang, et al., A survey on evaluation of large language models, *ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology* 15 (2024) 1–45.

[3] A. Radford, J. W. Kim, C. Hallacy, A. Ramesh, G. Goh, S. Agarwal, G. Sastry, A. Askell, P. Mishkin, J. Clark, G. Krueger, I. Sutskever, Learning transferable visual models from natural language supervision, in: Proceedings of the 38th International Conference on Machine Learning, volume 139 of *Proceedings of Machine Learning Research*, PMLR, 2021, pp. 8748–8763. URL: <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v139/radford21a.html>.

[4] N. Messina, M. Stefanini, M. Cornia, L. Baraldi, F. Falchi, G. Amato, R. Cucchiara, Aladin: Distilling fine-grained alignment scores for efficient image-text matching and retrieval, in: Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Content-based Multimedia Indexing, 2022, pp. 64–70. doi:10.1145/3549555.3549576.

[5] J. Li, D. Li, C. Xiong, S. Hoi, Blip: Bootstrapping language-image pre-training for unified vision-language understanding and generation, in: International conference on machine learning, PMLR, 2022, pp. 12888–12900.

[6] Y. Bai, X. Li, G. Wang, C. Zhang, L. Shang, J. Xu, Z. Wang, F. Wang, Q. Liu, Sparterm: Learning term-based sparse representation for fast text retrieval, arXiv preprint arXiv:2010.00768 (2020).

[7] T. Formal, B. Piwowarski, S. Clinchant, Splade: Sparse lexical and expansion model for first stage ranking, in: Proceedings of the 44th International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval, 2021, pp. 2288–2292.

[8] T. Formal, C. Lassance, B. Piwowarski, S. Clinchant, Towards effective and efficient sparse neural information retrieval, *ACM Transactions on Information Systems* 42 (2024) 1–46.

[9] G. Amato, F. Carrara, F. Falchi, C. Gennaro, L. Vadicamo, Large-scale instance-level image retrieval, *Inf. Process. Manage.* 57 (2020) 102100.

[10] G. Amato, P. Bolettieri, F. Carrara, F. Falchi, C. Gennaro, N. Messina, L. Vadicamo, C. Vairo, Visione 5.0: Enhanced user interface and ai models for vbs2024, in: International Conference on Multimedia Modeling, Springer, 2024, pp. 332–339.

[11] G. Amato, P. Bolettieri, F. Carrara, F. Falchi, C. G. CNR-ISTI, N. M. CNR-ISTI, Visione 5.0: Toward evaluation with novice users, in: 2024 International Conference on Content-Based Multimedia Indexing (CBMI), IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–6.

[12] G. Amato, P. Bolettieri, F. Carrara, F. Debole, F. Falchi, C. Gennaro, L. Vadicamo, C. Vairo, The VISIONE video search system: exploiting off-the-shelf text search engines for large-scale video retrieval, *Journal of Imaging* 7 (2021) 76.

[13] L. Vadicamo, R. Arnold, W. Bailer, F. Carrara, C. Gurin, N. Hezel, X. Li, J. Lokoc, S. Lubos, Z. Ma, et al., Evaluating performance and trends in interactive video retrieval: Insights from the 12th vbs competition, *IEEE Access* (2024).

[14] J. Lokoč, S. Andreadis, W. Bailer, A. Duane, C. Gurin, Z. Ma, N. Messina, T.-N. Nguyen, L. Peška, L. Rossetto, L. Sauter, K. Schall, K. Schoeffmann, O. S. Khan, F. Spiess, L. Vadicamo, S. Vrochidis, Interactive video retrieval in the

- age of effective joint embedding deep models: lessons from the 11th vbs, *Multimedia Systems* (2023). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00530-023-01143-5>. doi:10.1007/s00530-023-01143-5.
- [15] L. Rossetto, K. Schoeffmann, C. Gurrin, J. Lokoč, W. Bailer, Results of the 2024 video browser showdown, 2024. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.15683>. arXiv:2502.15683.
- [16] F. Carrara, C. Gennaro, L. Vadicamo, G. Amato, Vec2doc: transforming dense vectors into sparse representations for efficient information retrieval, in: *International Conference on Similarity Search and Applications*, Springer, 2023, pp. 215–222.
- [17] W. Shang, K. Sohn, D. Almeida, H. Lee, Understanding and improving convolutional neural networks via concatenated rectified linear units, in: *Proceedings of the 33rd International Conference on Machine Learning*, volume 48 of *ICML 2016*, JMLR.org, 2016, pp. 2217–2225.
- [18] P. Zezula, G. Amato, V. Dohnal, M. Batko, *Similarity search: the metric space approach*, volume 32, Springer Science & Business Media, 2006.
- [19] V. Pestov, Indexability, concentration, and vc theory, *Journal of Discrete Algorithms* 13 (2012) 2–18. doi:10.1016/j.jda.2011.10.002.
- [20] V. Mic, D. Novak, P. Zezula, Binary sketches for secondary filtering, *ACM Transactions on Information Systems (TOIS)* 37 (2018) 1–28.
- [21] N. Higuchi, Y. Imamura, V. Mic, T. Shinohara, K. Hirata, T. Kuboyama, Nearest-neighbor search from large datasets using narrow sketches., in: *ICPRAM*, 2022, pp. 401–410.
- [22] E. Chávez, K. Figueroa, G. Navarro, Effective proximity retrieval by ordering permutations, *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* 30 (2008) 1647–1658.
- [23] L. Vadicamo, C. Gennaro, F. Falchi, E. Chávez, R. Connor, G. Amato, Re-ranking via local embeddings: a use case with permutation-based indexing and the nsimplex projection, *Information Systems* 95 (2021) 101506.
- [24] D. Novak, P. Zezula, Ppp-codes for large-scale similarity searching, *Transactions on Large-Scale Data-and Knowledge-Centered Systems XXIV: Special Issue on Database-and Expert-Systems Applications* (2016) 61–87.
- [25] L. Vadicamo, R. Connor, E. Chávez, Query filtering using two-dimensional local embeddings, *Information Systems* 101 (2021) 101808.
- [26] C. Gennaro, G. Amato, P. Bolettieri, P. Savino, An approach to content-based image retrieval based on the lucene search engine library, in: *International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries*, Springer, 2010, pp. 55–66.
- [27] G. Amato, P. Bolettieri, F. Carrara, F. Falchi, C. Gennaro, Large-scale image retrieval with elasticsearch, in: *The 41st International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research & Development in Information Retrieval*, 2018, pp. 925–928.
- [28] F. Carrara, L. Vadicamo, C. Gennaro, G. Amato, Approximate nearest neighbor search on standard search engines, in: *Similarity Search and Applications: 15th International Conference, SISAP 2022, Bologna, Italy, October 5–7, 2022, Proceedings*, Springer, 2022, pp. 214–221.
- [29] G. Salton, M. J. McGill, *Introduction to Modern Information Retrieval*, McGraw-Hill, Inc., New York, NY, USA, 1986.
- [30] H. Zamani, M. Dehghani, W. B. Croft, E. Learned-Miller, J. Kamps, From neural re-ranking to neural ranking: Learning a sparse representation for inverted indexing, in: *Proceedings of the 27th ACM international conference on information and knowledge management*, 2018, pp. 497–506.
- [31] D. Povey, G. Cheng, Y. Wang, K. Li, H. Xu, M. Yarmohammadi, S. Khudanpur, Semi-orthogonal low-rank matrix factorization for deep neural networks., in: *Interspeech*, 2018, pp. 3743–3747.
- [32] S. Bruch, F. M. Nardini, C. Rulli, R. Venturini, Efficient inverted indexes for approximate retrieval over learned sparse representations, in: *Proceedings of the 47th International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval*, 2024, pp. 152–162.
- [33] J. Pennington, R. Socher, C. D. Manning, GloVe: global vectors for word representation, in: *Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP)*, 2014, pp. 1532–1543.
- [34] D. Dua, C. Graff, UCI machine learning repository, 2017. URL: <http://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml>.
- [35] C. Schuhmann, R. Beaumont, R. Vencu, C. Gordon, R. Wightman, M. Cherti, T. Coombes, A. Katta, C. Mullis, M. Wortsman, et al., Laion-5b: An open large-scale dataset for training next generation image-text models, *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* 35 (2022) 25278–25294.
- [36] A. Radford, J. W. Kim, C. Hallacy, A. Ramesh, G. Goh, S. Agarwal, G. Sastry, A. Askell, P. Mishkin, J. Clark, et al., Learning transferable visual models from natural language supervision, in: *International conference on machine learning*, PMLR, 2021, pp. 8748–8763.
- [37] T.-Y. Lin, M. Maire, S. Belongie, J. Hays, P. Perona, D. Ramanan, P. Dollár, C. L. Zitnick, Microsoft coco: Common objects in context, in: *Computer Vision—ECCV 2014: 13th European Conference, Zurich, Switzerland, September 6–12, 2014, Proceedings, Part V* 13, Springer, 2014, pp. 740–755.
- [38] B. Paria, C.-K. Yeh, I. E. Yen, N. Xu, P. Ravikumar, B. Póczos, Minimizing flops to learn efficient sparse representations, arXiv preprint arXiv:2004.05665 (2020).
- [39] M. Douze, A. Guzhva, C. Deng, J. Johnson, G. Szilvasy, P.-E. Mazaré, M. Lomeli, L. Hosseini, H. Jégou, The faiss library (2024). arXiv:2401.08281.